

Interactive Artificial Intelligence-based System for Depression

Degree in Computer Engineering

Final Degree Project

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To my tutor, Rodrigo, for his guidance throughout this process.

To all those who, with their valuable teachings, have contributed to my academic training.

To all the people who have supported me and helped me complete this path.

Thank you.

DOCUMENT OF ORIGINALITY

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Summary

According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO) [34], one in eight people worldwide suffers from mental health issues. Early identification of these problems is essential for addressing them. Among the most common mental health disorders are depression and anxiety, which affect over 280 million and 301 million people, respectively [13].

Among population groups, students are at risk of experiencing depression, stress, and anxiety due to factors such as academic pressure, uncertainty about the future, lack of sleep, or social isolation [2]. These factors make this group particularly vulnerable.

This study proposes a reinforcement learning-based approach for the analysis and detection of patterns related to depression among students. The study will be conducted using real data in CSV format collected from various sources, including relevant psychosocial variables. A custom environment will be built using the OpenAI Gym library. In this environment, an agent will operate, trained using the Deep Q-Learning reinforcement learning algorithm implemented with TensorFlow.

The aim is for the agent to learn to identify situations or combinations of factors that may be related to mental health risk conditions. The results will not only allow the evaluation of the model's validity but also provide understandable interpretations of the learned patterns. This study demonstrates how artificial intelligence can be applied as a tool in the field of mental health, offering means for the prevention and early detection of depression in an educational context.

Extended Abstract

In recent years, artificial intelligence (AI) has gained a leading role in developing innovative solutions, ranging from process automation to intelligent decision-making in complex environments. One of the fields in which its application is arousing special interest is mental health, for example, with gamification to promote mental health in university students [7], where the potential of AI to detect complex patterns, anticipate risks, and offer adaptive recommendations opens up new possibilities.

In this context, AI-based technologies can be trained to process large volumes of heterogeneous data that would otherwise be impossible for humans to analyze within a reasonable amount of time. This includes the analysis of medical records, emotional health questionnaires, digital behavior patterns, and physiological signals from wearables. The cross-referencing of these information sources enables the generation of predictive models capable of identifying early warning signs, personalizing therapeutic recommendations, and adapting interventions in real time.

In addition, AI makes it possible to replicate realistic environments through interactive simulations that facilitate safe experimentation with different intervention strategies. These simulations not only provide controlled environments to study the behavior of a complex system, such as mental well-being, but also allow the parameters of the environment to be precisely adjusted to evaluate clinical or pedagogical hypotheses. Thus, tools such as personalized environments in OpenAI Gym, combined with reinforcement learning algorithms, offer a fertile field for the development of automated solutions that learn adaptively based on the results obtained.

The integration of AI techniques in the educational and clinical fields also presents new opportunities for training professionals. For example, case simulation using intelligent agents can be used in teaching contexts for psychology, medicine, or pedagogy students to train diagnostic or strategic skills without the need to expose real patients. In the same way, the policies learned by agents can be analyzed to extract patterns that help to better understand the factors associated with the improvement of the emotional state, thus contributing to scientific knowledge and the continuous improvement of therapeutic practices.

Simultaneously, mental health problems, such as depression and anxiety, have experienced a worrying increase globally, especially among vulnerable populations, such as students. The WHO [34] estimates that more than 280 million people worldwide suffer from depression. This disorder profoundly affects how a person thinks, feels, and behaves, interfering with their ability to carry out daily activities. In young people, such as college students, depression can manifest in less visible but equally disruptive ways, such as social isolation, a decline in academic performance, or a prolonged lack of motivation. In addition, specific risk factors such as the transition to adulthood, academic pressure, insecurity about the future, economic difficulties, lack of sleep, and social isolation

increase the risk of psychological disorders [31]. The combination of the aforementioned factors means that this population requires priority attention in the design of early detection strategies and psycho-emotional interventions.

In this context, it is also relevant to note that depression, unlike other medical conditions, does not always present with biological markers or visible physical manifestations, which complicates its early diagnosis. Studies [2] have shown that many people affected by depression do not receive adequate treatment due to factors such as social stigmatization, lack of access to specialized resources, or lack of awareness of the initial symptoms. In the university environment, the pressure to maintain high academic performance, combined with the lack of strong support networks, contributes to these mental health problems going undetected until they reach critical levels. In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic has accentuated many of these conditions, causing an increase in the prevalence of disorders such as depression and anxiety, especially among young people. The disruption of social life, virtual classes, and economic uncertainty have been catalysts for prolonged emotional distress in students.

From a public health perspective, the effects of depression not only impact the quality of life of those who suffer from it but also the productive and educational fabric of societies. In the case of university students, lack of attention to these problems can result in school dropouts, deterioration in academic performance, difficulties in subsequent job placement, and even self-injurious or suicidal behavior. Therefore, addressing depression from an interdisciplinary approach and supported by innovative technological tools is not only a viable option but also an urgent need. At this point, artificial intelligence capabilities can play a key role in identifying risk patterns, generating early warnings, and offering guidance on possible support actions.

In this study, we propose a computational approach that combines real data and deep reinforcement learning (DRL) techniques to model scenarios of depression risk in students and simulate the application of intervention strategies. To this end, a personalized environment called *StudentDepressionEnv* was designed using the OpenAI Gym library. This environment simulates a student's state based on psychosocial variables obtained from a real dataset, representing characteristics such as academic pressure, sleep duration, eating habits, level of satisfaction with studies, and suicidal thoughts, among others. Through this environment, it is possible to systematically analyze the impact of various interventions on students' emotional well-being, which facilitates the interpretation of behavior and decision-making patterns from a computational perspective.

The AI agent deployed within this environment is based on the Deep Q-Learning (DQN) algorithm, a deep learning technique that allows the agent to learn an optimal policy by exploring the action space and evaluating the consequences of its decisions (rewards or penalties). However, throughout the study, other algorithms of the Q-Learning family are also discussed, including variants such as Double DQN or Hierarchical Q-Learning, comparing their theoretical foundations and practical applications. Different

experience memories for DQN are also considered, such as Experience Replay and Prioritized Experience Replay. This allowed us to contextualize the chosen algorithm and understand the reasons for its selection against available alternatives.

For the development and implementation of this project, various platforms and software libraries specialized in reinforcement learning were thoroughly explored and evaluated. Among the most prominent tools considered were TensorFlow, PyTorch, and StableBaselines3, each with unique advantages depending on the specific project requirements. The analysis focused on several key criteria, including the functionality offered by each library, their respective levels of abstraction (ranging from low-level model customization to high-level algorithm implementations), the ease of integration with custom environments such as those built in OpenAI Gym, and the quality and comprehensiveness of the documentation and community support available.

The agent interacts with the environment by simulating the application of different possible actions, such as offering psychological advice, reducing academic pressure, improving sleep or eating habits, among others. Each action has a potential effect on the student's condition and an associated reward based on its effectiveness in reducing the risk of developing depression. The learning process is based on the continuous improvement of the agent based on its previous experience, allowing it to identify optimal patterns of action that maximize the well-being of the simulated student.

One of the key characteristics of the environment is the implementation of penalty mechanisms for ineffective repetitive actions or for behavioral cycles that do not produce improvements, which allows the learning of more efficient and realistic strategies. In addition, completion criteria were incorporated to determine when the student had overcome depression. These criteria were built based on a combination of relevant variables such as the level of satisfaction with studies, sleep duration, and academic pressure, among others. Although it is recognized that in real life, overcoming a depressive condition cannot be defined so strictly, attempts have been made to establish thresholds that reflect a functionally positive state without requiring idealized or unrealistic conditions. In a study with a greater number of variables, more realistic conditions for overcoming could be established; however, in this case, with the variables obtained, a more realistic possible overcoming objective was established for this case. The selection of these conditions as part of our overcoming condition responds to a compromise between clinical realism and computational feasibility, recognizing that in a simulated environment, it is necessary to formalize goals that, although they may not capture the full complexity of the phenomenon, allow an objective evaluation of the agent's progress.

During the training phase, the agent was exposed to one thousand eight hundred and sixty-one episodes, which represented 10% of the entries in the total dataset, where it progressively learned to avoid counterproductive actions and prioritize interventions that favor the improvement of the student's condition. A neural network with several

hidden layers was used as an approximator of the Q function, and a prioritized experience buffer was implemented to improve the learning efficiency, allowing the most informative transitions to be sampled more frequently. This technical approach not only improves the speed of learning but also contributes to the stability of the neural network, thereby reducing the risk of the agent learning suboptimal or erratic policies.

After training, an evaluation phase was carried out in which the agent operated without random exploration (deterministic policy) on the rest of the entries in the dataset, 16745 in total. The results showed a success rate of 100%, understood as the proportion of episodes in which the agent managed to bring the student's condition to conditions considered non-depressive. In addition, the distribution of reasons for the completion of the episodes, average reward per episode, and actions most used by the agent were analyzed. It was observed that the most frequent actions in successful strategies were: reducing academic pressure, providing mental health counseling, improving sleep, improving nutrition, and giving scholarships or financial aid. These actions are consistent with actual clinical recommendations according to the various sources found. This type of consistency between what is learned by AI and the interventions endorsed by professional practice reinforces the validity of the proposed model.

Visualization tools were also implemented to graphically represent the use of actions, the evolution of the reward, and the impact of the different decisions made by the agent during training, showing whether or not the agent overcomes depression. These visualizations made it possible to interpret the behavior learned by the AI and detect common patterns among successful cases. Notably, differences were also observed in the sequences of actions applied in the few cases where progress was slower, which may offer useful clues for future refinement of the environment, the reward system, or the learning algorithm itself, ultimately improving overall performance and robustness.

On the other hand, it is important to note that the current model, although robust in its conception, operates in a simulated and controlled environment. The direct extrapolation of these results to real life should be performed with caution, considering the complexity and variability inherent in human behavior and clinical settings. However, the value of simulation lies precisely in allowing controlled experimentation and the formulation of hypotheses that can later be validated in real clinical or educational environments. These types of tools could be useful as valuable support for therapists, counselors, or researchers who seek to analyze intervention strategies in a noninvasive and low-cost manner.

This study demonstrates the potential of combining artificial intelligence (AI) and simulation techniques to address complex societal problems, such as mental health, from a computational perspective. The methodology developed can be extended and adapted to other contexts, such as providing support for professionals in decision-making processes, enabling the early detection of risk factors, or even serving as a pedagogical tool to raise awareness and promote understanding of mental health. In addition, it opens

new lines of interdisciplinary research aimed at leveraging intelligent agents in personalized, data-driven digital interventions.

In conclusion, the presented work offers an innovative, reproducible, and explainable approach to the use of reinforcement learning in the context of student mental health. Realistic case simulation and the agent's ability to learn optimal policies based on previous experiences represent a step towards the creation of technological tools that can complement traditional clinical strategies, especially in settings where human resources are limited. The integration of AI in this type of application does not seek to replace the role of health professionals but to offer additional support that allows intervention in an earlier, more personalized, and efficient way. This contributes to the consolidation of interdisciplinary approaches, where technology becomes an ally in improving students' emotional and cognitive well-being.

1. Introduction

Depression is a psychiatric and psychological diagnosis that refers to a mood disorder characterized by persistent sadness, loss of interest in everyday activities, fatigue, sleep disturbances, difficulty concentrating, and other symptoms. Anyone can be affected by depression, and more than 700,000 people die by suicide each year, making it the fourth leading cause of death among individuals aged 15–29 [34]. In academic settings, this disorder has become a growing concern, particularly among university students.

University students, being in a transitional stage of life, are particularly vulnerable to mental health issues such as depression and anxiety. Various international studies have shown an increase in the number of students suffering from depression and anxiety. Since they represent a crucial foundation for economic and social development, mental health problems in this population can profoundly impact their personal growth during early adulthood and university years, disrupting daily life and leading to negative emotional experiences, poor academic performance, insomnia, school dropout, and even suicidal tendencies. Therefore, identifying the factors that predict the onset of depression among university students is key to designing effective mental health prevention and intervention strategies [13].

Identifying this issue is essential to protect students' psychological well-being and ensure their academic and professional development. Mental health problems among university students can directly affect student retention, the quality of learning, and social integration within the educational community. A global report by UNESCO warns of an increase in the number of students experiencing at least one mental health issue, including depression, in the countries studied. In the United States, for example, 60% of students suffer from some form of mental health problem, representing a 50% increase since 2013. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly worsened this situation in many countries [31].

Although various strategies exist for addressing mental health in university settings, such as counseling services, awareness campaigns, and mindfulness programs, these approaches are often reactive, meaning they are implemented after symptoms have already appeared. Furthermore, many universities do not have adequate resources to offer timely and personalized psychological support to all students [33]. This highlights the need for innovative solutions that enable the early detection of risk patterns associated with depression.

This study proposes a reinforcement learning-based approach to analyze psychosocial variables and detect possible combinations of factors that may be related to depression among university students. Using real-world data in CSV format from various sources, a custom environment will be built using the OpenAI Gym library, where an

agent trained with a Deep Q-Learning (DQN) algorithm, implemented with TensorFlow, will learn to identify risk situations.

Through the created environment, the agent will apply different actions and learn—through feedback from the environment—which of these actions contribute to improving or worsening the simulated emotional state of a student. The aim was not to diagnose but to discover optimal intervention policies and preventive strategies, thereby identifying combinations of factors that could lead to a state of mental health risk. Thus, the model acts as a system that explores and optimizes interventions to be applied to students, supporting decision-making in educational and psychological contexts.

In this context, artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool to complement traditional strategies in the field of mental health. In this case, reinforcement learning offers a significant advantage: it allows for the modeling of dynamic interactions between multiple variables and the evaluation of the potential effects of different decisions or conditions on students' emotional well-being within a simulated environment. This ability to learn optimal strategies through experience makes it a valuable approach for investigating complex scenarios, such as depression prevention.

2. State of the Art

Recently, reinforcement learning (RL) has made remarkable progress owing to the emergence of innovative techniques that surpass traditional supervised and unsupervised learning approaches [11]. To delve into the various tools currently used for this type of learning, we begin with a brief introduction to the general behavior of reinforcement learning.

Reinforcement learning “consists of learning to decide, in a given situation, which action is most appropriate to achieve a goal” [6]. According to this definition, RL consists of two components: an agent that performs a series of actions and an environment in which the agent interacts. This environment contains the possible rules at each moment and holds the state in which the agent operates. To enable the agent to learn how to make decisions, both positive and negative rewards are given to inform it whether the action taken had a good or bad effect on the environment’s state. Figure 1 presents a graphical representation of this concept.

Figure 1: General model of reinforcement learning [16].

2.1.1. Q-Learning Algorithms

At the beginning of the project, research was conducted on the different ways to approach it, considering the possibility of using Reinforcement Learning (RL) or Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). As mentioned in the video presented by Antonio Manjavacas and Alejandro Campoy [19], classical RL algorithms that do not rely on neural networks offer good performance, although they present limitations when applied to large action or state spaces. Because it was unclear whether the states and actions in the case under study were too extensive for standard RL, information was gathered on these algorithms to determine which would best fit the problem, with a particular focus on Q-learning algorithms. This section analyzes both basic Q-learning and its extensions based on the information provided by Jang et al. [12].

- **Basic Q-Learning:** It uses a method called *off-policy* to separate the policy by which the agent selects actions from the policy it learns—that is, the one that updates the Q-values. This implies that taking poor actions does not affect the update of the agent’s current state Q-value. This algorithm uses a table to store the reward values for each state-action pair. The table is predefined and requires a considerable amount of memory for storage. In large environments with more states or multi-agent environments, large memory requirements can become problematic. The equation for the Q-value is as follows [12]:

$$Q(s, a) \leftarrow Q(s, a) + \alpha[R + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a') - Q(s, a)]$$

Where:

α is the learning rate, which has a value between 0 and 1.

R: a reward, and it is the rate of reduction of the reward as time goes on.

Q(s, a): value of the shares for the current state.

γ is the future value discount factor.

s’: next state after executing an action.

a’: possible actions in the subsequent state.

- **Deep Q-Learning:** This algorithm, developed by Google DeepMind, combines convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with the previous algorithm. In this case, the Q-function is approximately using a neural network rather than a table. Approximating the Q-value with a neural network is highly unstable, but experience replay helps to stabilize it. However, using excessive memory can reduce the learning speed.

The update of the network parameters is performed using the following formula [32]:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t + \alpha \left(Y_t^Q - Q(S_t, A_t; \theta_t) \right) \nabla_{\theta_t} Q(S_t, A_t; \theta_t).$$

Where:

θ_t : are the parameters (weights) of the neural network over time t .

θ_{t+1} : are the parameters updated after applying for a gradient.

α : learning rate, which controls the size of the step in the update.

Y_t : the target value is the estimated value that the network should have to improve its prediction.

$Q(S_t, A_t; \theta_t)$: current network-estimated Q-value for the state S_t and action A_t .

$\nabla_{\theta_t} Q(S_t, A_t; \theta_t)$: gradient of the Q-value with respect to the parameters, indicates the direction in which the weights should be adjusted to improve the prediction.

The Target Value Y_t is calculated as follows:

$$Y_t^Q \equiv R_{t+1} + \gamma \max_a Q(S_{t+1}, a; \theta_t)$$

Where:

R_{t+1} : obtained reward after performing the action A_t in the state S_t .

γ : discount factor. It determines the extent to which the future is valued compared to the present.

$\max_a Q(S_{t+1}, a; \theta_t)$: the highest possible Q-value in the next state S_{t+1} , considering all possible actions a .

This target value seeks to estimate the optimal expected return after taking the action A_t in the state S_t .

In the case of using a target network, as will be done in this study, the target value is calculated in a similar way:

$$Y_t^{DQN} \equiv R_{t+1} + \gamma \max_a Q(S_{t+1}, a; \theta_t^-)$$

In this case, a separate network with parameters (called a θ_t^- target network) is used, which is not constantly updated but every few steps. This makes the target more stable and prevents the network from chasing its erroneous estimates during training.

- **Hierarchical Q-Learning:** This hierarchical algorithm is designed to address problems that arise when the state and action spaces increase. It is an improvement over basic Q-learning, incorporating a hierarchical processing structure. Hierarchical Q-Learning does not have a single formula, but the main concept is abstract action, which divides the agent's action into higher and lower levels [12]:

- **High level:** Abstract objectives or goals.
- **Low level:** Physical actions to meet objectives.

For example, when the actions that the agent can choose are up, down, left, and right, and the goal is to reach the target point, the movement to the target point is at the upper level, and the up, down, left, and right movements comprise the lower level.

- **Double Q-Learning:** This algorithm was developed because Q-Learning performed poorly in stochastic problems due to the overestimation of the agent's action value. In other words, basic Q-learning did not seek an optimal value after a certain period but continuously selected the highest existing value. This algorithm addresses this issue by splitting the Q-learning value function that determines the action, thereby avoiding value bias in the algorithm. The rest of the algorithm is similar to Q-learning. The algorithm is as follows [12].

$$\begin{aligned} Q^A(s, a) &\leftarrow Q^A(s, a) + \alpha(s, a)(R + \gamma Q^B(s', a') - Q^A(s, a)) \\ Q^B(s, a) &\leftarrow Q^B(s, a) + \alpha(s, a)(R + \gamma Q^A(s', a') - Q^B(s, a)) \end{aligned}$$

Double Q-learning has two Q-functions, and each Q-function is updated with the value of another Q-function. The two Q-functions are important for learning from a separate set of experiences, but both value functions are used to choose the action.

2.1.2. Reinforcement learning development platforms

For the development of this project, research was conducted on various platforms where the agent could be implemented. A classification of development platforms for reinforcement learning was presented in [28].

- **TensorFlow** [30]: This open-source framework, maintained by Google, is very comprehensive for Machine Learning (ML). This allows users to create static data flow graphs that describe how information moves through the model. Within this framework, a very popular tool for building neural networks is Keras, which is designed to be user-friendly and allows integration with prebuilt models in TensorFlow, making deep learning work more accessible. This platform was chosen for implementation.
- **PyTorch** [20]: A more user-friendly tool developed by Meta that allows for the rapid prototyping of models. Unlike TensorFlow, PyTorch uses dynamic computation graphs that enable users to observe the model's progress during runtime. In terms of deep neural network capabilities, it offers functionality comparable to TensorFlow and Keras.
- **Stablebaselines3** [27]: This is a collection of ready-to-use reinforcement learning algorithms. This version was created to work with PyTorch, although the first version was built using TensorFlow. This allows for the quick and intuitive implementation of algorithms.

2.1.3. Simulation environment

Simulating an environment in which an agent can operate is essential, as it allows the agent to interact through trial and error without real-world risks. Environments are also useful for testing how real-world settings should be designed to achieve better results with an agent. OpenAI Gym is one of the most widely used and easiest environments to understand, which is why it was chosen from the beginning.

In the article by Brockman [3], OpenAI Gym is presented as a tool for reinforcement learning research, in which some design decisions of this tool are as follows:

- It focuses exclusively on environments and not on the implementation of RL algorithms.
- Emphasize sample complexity, not just final performance. Performance in an environment can be measured in two ways: final performance (average reward per episode) or learning time (sample complexity). Sample complexity, simply put, refers to counting the number of episodes required to surpass a predefined average performance threshold.
- Encourage peer review, not competition. The OpenAI Gym website allows users to compare the performance of their algorithms with the aim of promoting code and idea sharing and serving as a benchmark for evaluating different methods.
- Strict versioning of the environment. If the environment changes, the results before and after the change become incomparable owing to version differences. Therefore, it is ensured that any environment modification is accompanied by an increase in the number of versions.
- Default monitoring. The environments were implemented using a monitor that recorded every time step and reset.

OpenAI Gym includes implementations of environments for Atari games, Box2D, and Toy Text, among others. All environments can be viewed on the official website [5]. Figure 2 shows a part of the collection of environments that are part of the OpenAI Gym.

Figure 2: Some OpenAI Gym environments [3].

3. Analysis of objectives and methodology

3.1. Objectives

The ultimate goal of this undergraduate thesis is to understand and develop a reinforcement learning model capable of simulating the emotional evolution of students based on a series of actions applied to them. With this model, once trained, it would be possible to test real student cases where the actions suggested by the agent could be applied to improve and overcome depression. To achieve this general objective, it will be divided into a series of specific goals.

3.1.1. Obtaining the data

The first objective of developing the model was to obtain data that could be used to train it. For this purpose, the more data available, the better the model will be trained. Therefore, the main idea was to obtain a dataset with a large number of entries containing relevant information about emotional states and behaviors. The goal of this part was to obtain a dataset with these characteristics in '.csv' format that could be read and processed.

3.1.2. Prepare the data

Once the dataset has been obtained, the objective will be to analyze and prepare it so that only the relevant data is available, removing metadata that is unnecessary for training and variables with many null values that would not add much value to the model. This data will be converted into the most suitable format for use within the environment.

3.1.3. Build the environment

With the data ready to work with, the next step will be to create the environment in GYM, where a series of actions will be implemented that the agent can take. These actions influence the student's state either positively or negatively, depending on the chosen action. Each action has a corresponding reward, which informs the agent whether the action taken produces a good or bad result. The actions will be applied to a random entry from the dataset, which will also be selected by the environment itself.

3.1.4. Designing the agent

The agent to be implemented using TensorFlow will perform actions on different entries to learn to make useful decisions for each situation. The aim is to build an agent that not only detects the state of depression but also learns what to do in each case to achieve positive and long-term outcomes.

3.2. Methodology

This section provides a detailed description of the process followed for the development of this project. To do so, the various sub-objectives defined in the previous section are addressed in an orderly manner, as they contribute to achieving the overall goal of this project. The process includes everything from the collection and preparation

of the necessary data to the implementation of the simulation environment and design of the agent. Each of these phases is essential for ensuring the correct execution and evaluation of the proposed system.

3.2.1. Data collection

Initially, an attempt was made to carry out the project using biomedical data from patients with depression. However, due to the lack of response from the platforms consulted, it was not possible to access such data. Faced with this situation, other alternatives were explored, such as databases containing social media posts from individuals with depression. Ultimately, a different dataset was chosen, which proved to be more suitable for the development of this project.

The data used was obtained from surveys conducted with students, in which they were evaluated based on whether they met certain criteria or the degree to which they did. All surveys indicated whether the student had depression or not. Various sources of this type of data were identified: some datasets had few entries but many variables, whereas others had many entries but few variables. To obtain a more complete dataset with richer variables, several datasets were combined. The following datasets were used:

1. The data from shariful07 [26] include information on age, gender, field of study, academic year, marital status, and whether the individual has depression, anxiety, panic attacks, or is seeing a specialist.
2. The data obtained from [24] contained five numerical variables (age, academic pressure, study satisfaction, study hours, and financial stress) and six categorical variables (gender, sleep duration, eating habits, suicidal thoughts, family history, and depression).
3. The data used were obtained from a study on anxiety, stress, and depression among university students [29].
4. The last dataset used was obtained from a study on student depression [1]. This dataset has the highest number of entries among those mentioned.

3.2.2. Description of the dataset

Once the four data sets were merged into a single file, variables in some data sets were adapted to have the same type of values and the maximum number of values per column. The following modifications were made:

First, the empty cells were filled with 'ND', indicating that the data was not available. After that, in the third dataset [29], based on its 'Depression Label' variable—which indicated the student's level of depression—the 'Depression' column was filled in. This column was not originally present in the dataset. All entries were filled with 'Yes', except for the rows where the 'Depression Label' was 'No depression'; in those cases, they were filled with 'No'

In addition to this same dataset, the "Suicidal thoughts" column was completed based on the dataset column that indicated whether he had thought he would be better off dead or hurting himself. Also in this set, age was given by age ranges, so it was decided to generate a random value within each range.

From the second set [1], the binary data in the "Depression" column was converted to "Yes" and "No" so that they would have the same format as the rest.

Once this was completed, the only subsequent modification was made during the analysis of the data, when it detected the existence of 7 entries in the "Age" column that did not have an exact value and had values "Above 30" and "Below 18". These rows were modified, leaving the value 30 or 18, depending on the case.

The dataset consisted of a total of 30531 entries with 32 columns. Table 1 shows the description of the total number of variables in the set.

Table 1

Description of the dataset variables

Name	Description	Data type	Available data
Title	Name of the study or article from which the data are obtained	String	30531
Abstract	Brief description of the dataset	String	30531
Date	Date of publication of the study or article	Date	30531
Source	Study Link	String	30531
Author(s)	Study Author	String	30531
Gender	Student gender	"Male," "Female," "Prefer not to say"	30531
Age	Student age	Int	30531
Education	Studies he is studying	String	30029

Name	Description	Data type	Available data
Academic year	Year of the course you are in	String	2129
Exemption or scholarship	Indicate if you have received an exemption or scholarship at the university	"Yes", "No"	2129
Little interest or pleasure	How often in a semester you have little interest or pleasure in doing things.	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Depressed, discouraged, or hopeless	How often in a semester the student has felt depressed, discouraged, or hopeless	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Trouble sleeping	How often in a semester the student has had trouble falling asleep or staying asleep, or has slept too much	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Tired or low energy	How often in a semester the student has felt tired or low on energy	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Poor appetite or overeating	How often in a semester the student	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129

Name	Description	Data type	Available data
	has had a lack of appetite or overeaten		
Feeling bad about yourself, failure, or disappointment	How often in a semester the student has felt bad about himself, failed, or is a disappointment to himself or his family	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Trouble concentrating	How often in a semester the student has had trouble concentrating on things like reading, watching movies, etc.	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Thoughts of being better off dead or self-harm	How often in a semester the student has thought he or she would be better off dying or hurting himself	0 (never) a 3 (every day)	2129
Academic pressure	Academic pressure of the student	1 (low) a 5 (high)	28402
Satisfaction with studies	Student Study Satisfaction	1 (low) a 5 (high)	28402
Study hours	Working hours per day	Int	28402
Financial stress	Financial stress	1 (low) a 5 (high)	28402
Married	Indicate whether or not you are married	"Yes", "No"	101

Name	Description	Data type	Available data
Eating habits	What are your eating habits like?	"Moderate", "Healthy", "Unhealthy"	28402
Sleep duration	Hours of sleep per day	"Less than 5 hours", "5-6 hours", "7-8 hours", "More than 8 hours"	28402
Depression	Indicates if you have depression	"Yes", "No"	30531
Depression Label	Degree of depression	"moderate", "mild," "severe," "no depression"	2028
Anxiety	Indicates if you have anxiety	"Yes," "No"	101
Panic attacks	Indicates if you have panic attacks	"Yes", "No"	101
Specialist	Indicates whether you have seen a specialist to treat your condition	"Yes", "No"	101
Suicidal thoughts	If the person has had suicidal thoughts	"Yes", "No"	30430
Family history	Family history of mental illness	"Yes", "No"	28402

3.2.3. Preprocessing

The first thing that was done after reading the data was to delete the columns that contained metadata about the study (the columns: 'Title', 'Abstract', 'Date', 'Source',

'Author(s)'), but they had no direct relationship with the student's emotional state and, therefore, did not contribute anything to the model. Then, all the "ND" values were replaced with NaN values, since machine learning models do not understand "ND", so the conversion of that value to a null value that Python and pandas do understand: NaN.

After obtaining the number of null values present in each column, we proceeded to eliminate from the set those variables whose proportion of missing data exceeded the proportion of available data. Consequently, the following columns were deleted: 'Academic year', 'Exemption or scholarship', 'Little interest or pleasure', 'Depressed, discouraged or hopeless', 'Trouble sleeping', 'Tired or low energy', 'Poor appetite or overeating', 'Feeling bad about yourself, a failure, or disappointment', 'Trouble concentrating', 'Thoughts of being better off dead or self-harm', 'Married', 'Depression Label', 'Anxiety', 'Panic Attacks' and 'Specialist'. This decision was based on the considerable number of null values present in these columns.

Once the previous variables were eliminated, the remaining columns were processed. First, the numerical columns were identified and converted to numerical variables; for these, their null values were filled with the value of their mean. The numerical variables considered were: 'Age', 'Academic pressure', 'Satisfaction with studies', 'Study hours', and 'Financial stress'. Of the above, all except 'Age' and 'Study hours' were integer values from 1 to 5, so once the null values were filled with their meaning, the value obtained was rounded to have it as an integer.

The columns 'Depression', 'Suicidal thoughts', and 'Family history' were then converted to binary variables, replacing "yes" with a 1 and "no" with a 0. For the binary variables 'Suicidal thoughts' and 'Family history', missing values were imputed using the mode of each respective column.

During the analysis of the columns to identify those of a categorical type, it was observed that the columns 'Eating habits' and 'Sleep duration' contained a few entries that had the value "Others"; the number of entries with this value was 12 and 18, respectively. Since these represented a very small proportion of the total and did not provide relevant information, it was decided to treat them as null values.

Once all the columns were reviewed, the following were defined as categorical variables: 'Gender', 'Eating habits', 'Sleep duration', and 'Education'. The null values present in these variables were completed using the value of the mode of each column. Once this was done, there were no more null values left in the dataset.

To work better with the data, it was decided to encode the categorical variables by assigning numbers to each text value. When performing the analysis, it was observed that the column 'Education' presented a large number of possible values, many of which corresponded to the same branch of study. For this reason, these values were generalized and grouped into 11 categories: 'engineering', 'islamic education', 'computer science',

'law', 'science', 'other', 'business', 'psychology', 'health sciences', 'social sciences' and 'education'. Each category was assigned a numerical value without following a preferential order.

Regarding the rest of the variables, specific numerical values were assigned for each case, ensuring coherent and adequate coding for subsequent analysis. These assignments were made as follows:

- 'Gender' column: "Male" = 0, "Female" = 1 and "Prefer not to say" = 2.
- 'Eating habits' column: "Unhealthy" = 0, "Moderate" = 1, "Healthy" = 2.
- 'Sleep duration' column: "Less than 5 hours" = 0, "5-6 hours" = 1, "7-8 hours" = 2, "More than 8 hours" = 3.

By having the values of the categorical variables represented numerically, the creation of the environment is facilitated, allowing rewards to be established and states to be modified based on the agent's actions in a simpler and more efficient way.

Once all the variables were treated, it was decided to eliminate the entries that contained data from students who did not have depression, since the agent would have nothing to do with them as they were in a non-depressive state.

To finalize the data preparation, it was decided to separate the dataset into two subsets: a training set that will account for 10% of the total data, and a validation set consisting of the remaining 90% of inputs. This division allows the performance of the model to be evaluated by testing its behavior on states that were not seen during the learning process.

3.2.4. Creating the environment in Gym

The goal of this environment is to be able to simulate the variations in the state of a student with depression depending on the possible interventions (actions). This environment will serve to train the implemented agent and for it to learn policies to improve the mental state of the students. For the development of the environment, a use case (See Annex 1) provided by the tutor, Rodrigo, was taken as a basis. This case served as a guide to properly structure and guide the simulation and the possible actions of the agent.

In order to facilitate the understanding of the developed environment, the explanation has been structured into different sections.

3.2.4.1. Logic of an episode

An episode is defined as a process of intervention on the status of a student selected from the dataset. A maximum number of actions that an agent could perform of up to 150 per episode was established (this is indicated by the variable *max_step*), considering that,

given the number of possible actions, this value is reasonable. An episode ends if any of the following three conditions are met:

- **The student overcomes depression.** The conditions that indicate a significant improvement in the psychological state are met.
- **Maximum steps are reached.** As many actions have been performed as the parameter allows, *max_step*.
- **A loop or oscillation with no progress is detected.** Stagnation is penalized, ending the episode if there are no relevant changes.

The following sections will detail how each of these conditions can be achieved.

3.2.4.2. Representation of the state of the environment

The environment is represented by a continuous state vector, which is returned at each step for the people. This vector contains the normalized values of the 12 attributes that describe the psychological, academic, and personal state of the student, corresponding to the variables of the dataset. The generation of this vector is carried out through the *_get_obs()* function (Annex 2).

The decision to normalize the data within the environment, rather than during the preprocessing of the data, was made during the deployment phase. This choice was based on the observation that it was significantly easier to change the student's state after the execution of an action when the data was not normalized. In addition, this strategy facilitated the debugging tasks, since the unnormalized values allowed the changes produced in each attribute of the student's state to be more clearly identified.

3.2.4.3. Space for possible actions and interventions

The agent has 13 discrete actions, identified by indexes from 0 to 12, which represent different types of interventions. These actions are designed to influence the student's status in a variety of ways, as detailed in Table 2.

Table 2

Actions of the environment

ID	Action	Expected effect
0	Decrease academic pressure	Decreases academic pressure If the above decreases, then: Study satisfaction increases, and study hours are reduced
1	Increase academic pressure	Academic pressure increases If you increase the above, then: Decreased study satisfaction and increased study hours

ID	Action	Expected effect
2	Provide mental health counseling	Suicidal thoughts decrease
3	Do not provide mental health counseling	The problem is ignored
4	Improve sleep	Increases sleep duration
5	Worsen sleep	Decreases sleep duration
6	Improve diet	Eating habits increase, that is, they improve
7	Worsen diet	Eating habits decrease, that is, they worsen
8	Exercise	Increases sleep duration
9	Provide scholarship/financial aid	Decreases financial stress
10	Peer support	Increases study satisfaction
11	Time management training	Study hours are reduced, and academic pressure is reduced
12	Do nothing (zero action)	Nothing is done

The selection of these actions was based on the review of various articles that analyze positive or negative effects of different interventions on depression:

- **Academic pressures and economic difficulties:** According to UNESCO [31], these factors are decisive in the appearance of mental health problems among students: “numerous factors contribute to the mental health challenges faced by

students, including academic pressures, financial difficulties”. Therefore, it is considered that interventions aimed at reducing these pressures can have a positive impact on the student's condition, and that, on the contrary, increasing these can have a negative impact.

- **Eating habits:** In the article by Ramón Arbués et al. [21], it is indicated that in the university environment, it is common to find unhealthy eating habits, which have been linked to high levels of anxiety, stress, and depressive symptoms. Implementing educational programs that encourage better nutrition among students could contribute positively to their psychological well-being, and vice versa. Therefore, actions aimed at improving diet, assuming improvements, and worsening diet, establishing that it negatively affects them, were included.
- **Sleep duration:** In the article by Cano-Lozano et al. [4], it is estimated that about 80% of individuals who present depressive symptoms manifest significant difficulties related to the quantity and quality of sleep. This suggests that actions that promote better rest can contribute to improving the student's psychological state.
- **Peer support:** It has been observed that maintaining relationships with peers and friends who have positive characteristics tends to be related to a lower presence of depressive symptoms. On the other hand, when friendships have negative traits, these are usually associated with an increase in these symptoms [10]. Therefore, it was considered relevant to include actions that promote social support and positive intervention among students, assuming that peer help in the student environment can help them feel more satisfied with studying.
- **Provide mental health counseling:** According to Gempeler [8], after the application of certain types of therapy, a reduction in suicidal behaviors was observed compared to other therapeutic approaches. Although the article compares the effectiveness of therapies, it is based on the general assumption that going to therapy contributes to reducing suicidal thoughts. For this reason, a mental health counseling action was included that specifically improves this attribute. In addition, an additional reward is given if the student has a related family history, in order to reflect a greater potential impact on the intervention. Mental health counseling can help improve any of the attributes of the job, but so that the agent does not focus only on executing this action, only the improvement of suicidal thoughts and family history will be assumed.
- **Other actions:** The rest of the actions were defined from fragments of articles already mentioned, such as that of Beiter [2]. These include the action of “Do nothing,” which is considered harmful, as it involves ignoring the problem and not applying any improvement to the students’ condition, which reflects negatively on the reward.

The actions are executed by calling the `_aplicar_accion()` function (Annex 2), which returns if a change has occurred in the student's status (Boolean variable *change*) and the immediate reward for its effect (reward variable). In the following code snippet

(Figure 3), you can see actions 2 and 3, in which the value of the *change* variable is established and its respective reward for the action is also established. The rest of the implementation can be seen in Annex 2.

```
# 2 - Provide mental health counseling
elif action == 2:
    info["action"] = "Provide mental health counseling"

    if s["suicidal_thoughts"] == 1:
        s["suicidal_thoughts"] = 0
        reward += 1.0
        info["reduced_thoughts"] = True
        if s["family_history"] == 1:
            reward += 0.1
        change = True

# 3 - Do not provide mental health counseling
elif action == 3:
    info["action"] = "Do not provide mental health counseling"
    if s["depression"] == 1:
        reward -= 1.0
        info["penalizacion"] = "ignore depression"
        change = False
    else:
        info["no_change"] = "there was no depression"
```

Figure 3: Partial implementation of the `_apply_action()` function. Source: own elaboration.

3.2.4.4. Rewards and Penalties

The reward system is an essential component of the environment, as it defines the agent's learning objective and guides their behavior to establish policies that benefit the student's psychological state. Through rewards, the aim is to encourage actions that contribute to improving the student's condition and to penalize those that are harmful, ineffective, or redundant.

In the environment, effective actions generate rewards proportional to their impact:

- **Decrease academic pressure:** up to a maximum of 0.55.
- **Provide mental health counseling:** up to a maximum of 1.1.
- **Improve sleep:** 0,5.
- **Improve diet:** 0,5.
- **Exercise:** 0,2.
- **Provide scholarship/financial aid:** 0,4.
- **Peer support:** 0,3.
- **Time management training:** 0,1.

Negative actions will be penalized as follows:

- **Increase academic pressure:** up to a maximum of -0,55.

- **Do not provide mental health counseling:** -1,0.
- **Worsen sleep:** -0,5.
- **Worsen diet:** -0,5.
- **Do nothing:** -0,2.

These rewards seek to reinforce desirable behaviors, causing the agent to converge towards desirable policies and avoid maintaining passive or harmful behaviors.

In addition to the rewards for actions, penalties were incorporated to discourage certain unwanted behaviors, such as reaching the maximum number of steps, repetition of actions, the absence of changes in the student's status, and oscillations in their evolution.

The episode will be terminated if the agent executes more than 150 steps without achieving the necessary conditions to overcome the depression, provided that the episode does not end due to an oscillating loop. If the reward accrued at that time is negative, which would indicate that the goal has not been reached and that they have performed more negative actions than positive ones, it will be penalized with -1.0. Conversely, if the step limit is reached, but the cumulative reward is positive, no penalty will be applied, as it will not be considered a failed episode.

When an action does not produce any state change (indicated by the variable *change* mentioned in the previous section), an extra penalty of -0.2 will be imposed. An additional cumulative penalty of up to 0.5 will be applied when there is no change in the next execution and the same action is repeated. This is implemented using a hash key, using an action history that combines the action and the observed state. If it detects that an action has already been applied multiple times and has not affected the state, it will be penalized more intensely. The implementation of these penalties can be seen in Figure 4.

```
# if the action did not change anything in the student's status, the student is penalized
if not change_occurred:
    self.repetitions_without_effect += 1
    reward -= 0.2 * self.repetitions_without_effect
    info["no_change"] = "action without effect"

    # if the action had no effect and is repeated, it is penalized more to avoid the loop
    repetitions = self.history_actions[obs_key]
    if repetitions > 1:
        penalty_loop = (repetitions - 1) * 0.5
        reward -= penalty_loop
        info["penalty_loop"] = f"-{penalty_loop:.2f}"
    else:
        self.repetitions_without_effect = 0
```

Figure 4: A snippet of code that performs the repetition penalty without any changes. Source: own elaboration

The decision to incorporate this additional penalty was made after observing the behavior of the agent during execution, where it was detected that, in certain cases, it

entered a loop, continuously repeating the same action without generating significant changes in the student's state.

In case of oscillations, the environment keeps a record of the students' last 10 states. If these states are found to be virtually identical, the agent is considered to be trapped in a loop of action with no real impact. The penalty for oscillations is -5.0, a fairly high penalty for the agent to avoid these behaviors. In addition, it was decided to end episodes with these conditions early, since the cyclical behavior of the agent only slowed down the training process.

The implementation of this functionality, visible in Figure 5, was possible through the use of a buffer that stores the last 10 states that we call *history_states*. This behavior was added to the environment by observing that, once the problem of repetition of actions was solved, the agent tended to enter loops in which, although there were state changes, they did not represent a real improvement. A concrete example was the alternation between the actions “Improve diet” and “Worsen diet”, which generated changes in the state without a significant effect on the student's evolution.

```
# if there is no progress, that is, the state does not change significantly in the last 10 steps,
# a penalty is imposed and the execution is terminated.
if len(self.history_states) == self.history_states.maxlen:
    changes = [not np.allclose(self.history_states[i], self.history_states[i + 1], atol=1e-3)
               for i in range(len(self.history_states) - 1)]
    if sum(changes) <= 1: # very few changes => oscillating loop
        done = True
        reward -= 5.0
        info["final_reason"] = "Oscillation without progress"
        info["penalty_oscillating_loop"] = True
```

Figure 5: A snippet of code that performs oscillation penalty. Source: own elaboration

3.2.4.5. Condition of success

In the designed environment, the condition of success of the episode occurs when a student manages to overcome depression. This is not based solely on an isolated action by the agent, but on the achievement of a set of conditions that reflect an improvement in the student's condition. This condition, implemented within the *step()* method, is evaluated after each action.

Although it is recognized that the conditions marked to overcome depression may not lead to overcoming it in a real case, we have tried to be as realistic as possible in the choice of the conditions that indicate that depression has been overcome. These conditions are:

- Sleep duration equal to or greater than 2 (on a scale of 0 to 3).
- Eating habits equal to or greater than 1 (on a scale of 0 to 2).

- Academic pressure equal to or less than 2 (on a scale of 1 to 5).
- Financial stress equal to or less than 2 (on a scale of 1 to 5).
- Absence of suicidal thoughts.

The established conditions present a set of variables that, together, simulate a state in which there are no factors that are either very negative or realistically perfect. It could have been chosen to set the goal of having the maximum attributes in a positive way under the conditions, but it was established that it was not a realistic goal. If it had been possible to obtain data with more variables, a somewhat more realistic goal could be defined. However, with the data obtained, it was considered that these conditions indicate a good state for any student, although unfortunately, sometimes it is not enough to overcome problems such as depression.

If all the conditions are met, the episode will end, and a reward of 10.0 will be established, a very high reward compared to the rest, but this will serve to help the agent try to get this great reward.

3.2.5. Agent Design

The implemented agent corresponds to a deep reinforcement learning model based on Deep Q-Networks (DQN), with enhancements such as Prioritized Experience Replay, Double DQN, soft update of the target network, and a ϵ -greedy policy adapted to valid actions. The agent is designed to learn how to solve the environment explained in the previous section, and just as the environment tried to solve different loops and oscillations, this agent will have a special focus on avoiding ineffective actions and improving training efficiency.

3.2.5.1. *Q Model Architecture*

The Q model is created with the function `create_q_model()`. This function constructs and returns a deep neural network model that represents the Q-value function. This function “Q (s, a)” estimates the expected value of reward that the agent can obtain by taking a specific action “a” in a given state “s”.

The function takes input parameters: a tuple (`input_shape`), which represents the shape of the input state, and an integer (`action_space`), which indicates how many possible actions the agent can take; this number determines the size of the output layer. To understand it better, the values that the input variables of the environment would take are presented below: `input_shape` will be “(12,)”, since the variables that make up the state vector are 12. This means that the network expects to receive a vector of 12 values as input at each time step; `action_space` will be 13, which is the number of possible actions to be carried out in the environment.

As for the architecture of the model, shown in Annex 3, we have:

- The input layer, which defines the shape of the state that the agent receives. This layer doesn't do anything; it just specifies the input dimension.

- A first hidden layer of 128 neurons with ReLu activation (Rectified Linear Unit), which introduces nonlinearity and helps learn complex representations.
- Second and third hidden layers, these are two consecutive layers of 64 neurons each that also use ReLu. These layers allow the network to learn more abstract and deeper patterns of the environment.
- The output layer, which contains as many neurons as possible actions (indicated by *action_space*). In this one, activation is linear because the Q values can be positive or negative. Each neuron represents the estimated Q-value for a specific action in the current state.

This structure was chosen for its moderate depth, since having three hidden layers allows you to capture non-linear relationships without easily overfitting. The structure explained was not the one chosen at first: first, tests were carried out with only two layers of size 32, then, when it was observed that the result was not as expected, the size of these was increased to 64, but the result hardly improved. Finally, it was decided to add a larger first hidden layer, and with this, both the result and the execution time improved significantly.

In Figure 6, you can see a visual diagram generated by Copilot [9], requested to show more clearly the architecture of the model, being able to see how the final layer would look.

Figure 6: Visual diagram of the architecture of the Q model [9].

3.2.5.2. Prioritized Experience Replay

In deep reinforcement learning algorithms such as DQN, an Experience Replay memory is used to store transitions of the type: (state, action, reward, next_state, done). This allows breaking the temporal correlation between experiences and reusing past experiences to improve learning efficiency [25].

Experience Replay selects experiences randomly. Initially, this type of memory was implemented to do the job, but after several executions in which the model continued to make numerous failures, it was decided to implement a priority memory, the Prioritized

Experience Replay which, unlike the previous one, assigns a priority to experiences based on their temporary error (TD error). Experiences with higher errors are more informative, and therefore more likely to be sampled.

As can be seen in Annex 4, this buffer is implemented as a class that contains the necessary logic to store and manage the agent's experiences during training. Its main methods and functionalities are briefly described below:

- *_init_ (self, max_size, alpha=0.6)*: For the implementation of this buffer, a list will be initialized to store the experiences, another to store the associated priorities, the maximum size of the buffer, and a variable called *alpha*. The *alpha* variable controls how much priority influences, for example, if *alpha* = 0, then sampling would be totally random, and if *alpha* = 1, sampling would be completely priority-based. To have a midpoint, it was decided to set the value of the variable to 0.6.
- *add (self, experience, td_error=1.0)*: It adds a new experience to the buffer by calculating its priority from the TD (Temporal Difference) error, and it is stored next to the experience. If the buffer is full, the oldest experience (FIFO) is deleted.
- *sample (self, batch_size)*: Function in charge of selecting a batch of experiences proportional to their priorities. It performs a stochastic sampling of experiences, where the probability of being selected is determined by their relative priorities. It returns both the samples, which will be as many as indicated by the input parameter *batch_size*, and the corresponding indexes.
- *update_priorities (self, indices, td_errors)*: It allows you to update the priorities of specific experiences, after they have been used in a training step, based on their new TD errors.
- *size (self)*: Returns the current number of experiences stored in the buffer.

This structure allows the agent to focus on those experiences that have a greater impact on improving their policy, thus accelerating the learning process. Therefore, with this priority buffer, you will get more efficient learning (it focuses on the most useful experiences), better memory use by avoiding training with uninformative data, and better adaptability, since priorities are dynamically updated.

3.2.5.3. Enhanced ϵ -Greedy Policy

The ϵ -greedy policy is a fundamental strategy in reinforcement learning to balance exploration (trying new actions) and exploitation (using learned knowledge to obtain rewards). This version of the policy also incorporates a mechanism to avoid certain ineffective or invalid actions, thus improving the efficiency of learning in the environment.

The implementation of this policy can be seen in Annex 5, in which it is decided with a priority ϵ whether exploration or exploitation is carried out:

- If ϵ is greater than a random number (between 0 and 1), it is explored by randomly choosing one of the available actions.

- In case the number generated is greater than ϵ , exploitation will be carried out, in which the agent will choose the best action according to the Q model, penalizing invalid actions.

Therefore, it is explored with probability ϵ and exploited with probability $(1-\epsilon)$. Figure 7 shows a simple diagram, generated by ChatGPT [15], to facilitate the understanding of the section.

Figure 7: Improved ϵ -greedy policy flowchart [15].

This approach allows the agent to explore the environment in a controlled manner while avoiding making previously detected errors, such as repeating actions that do not cause changes to the environment or that generate loops. Invalid actions will be flagged during training thanks to the information given by the environment when detecting loop or oscillation behaviors.

3.2.5.4. Soft update

In the DQN algorithm, two neural networks are used:

1. Main model (online): In implementation is called *model*, which learns and is continuously trained with the experiences that the agent collects from the environment.
2. Target model: In implementation, *target_model* is used to calculate the target values (Q-target) during training, updating every few steps.

The classic version of DQN makes a direct copy of the weights from the main model to the target model every few steps. This method can cause instability in training due to large changes in the goals that the model is trying to achieve.

Instead of replacing all the weights of the target model at once, the *soft_update()* function (See Annex 6) updates by mixing the previous weights of the target model with the new ones of the main model. This is done by the following formula [23]:

$$\theta_{\text{target}} \leftarrow \tau \cdot \theta_{\text{online}} + (1 - \tau) \cdot \theta_{\text{target}}$$

Where:

- τ : is the soft update coefficient; in this case, $\tau=0.01$ was chosen, a small value to avoid abrupt changes by smoothing out the variability between the steps.
- θ_{online} : are the current weights of the main model.
- θ_{target} : are the old weights of the objective model.

The gentle updating of the target model values is not done at each step of the training, but is executed periodically, specifically, every 5 steps. This allows the target model to remain constant for a while, allowing it to be tested, have more results, and prevent it from being constantly modified.

3.2.5.5. *Agent Training*

Agent training is at the core of the reinforcement learning process. During this stage, the agent interacts with the environment, collects experiences, updates its policy, and progressively improves its performance in the task.

The implementation (See Annex 7), as already mentioned, is based on the Deep Q-Network, with the improvements explained in the previous sections. The improvement of Double DQN, the theoretical basis of which was explained above (See Section 2.1.1), was also added.

The agent training process can be organized in a clear structure, which is repeated during each of the episodes defined by the parameter *num_episodes*, which in this case is equal to 1861, which corresponds to 10% of the total entries in the dataset. Here's a step-by-step breakdown of what happens within each training episode:

1. **Restarting the environment** (using *env.reset()*) **and recovery from the initial state for execution**. In this way, a new initial state is obtained for each episode.
2. **Step-by-step interaction**: The agent performs a series of steps until the environment indicates that it has finished (*done=True*). At every step:
 - a. Select an action using the ϵ -greedy policy.
 - b. Execute the action in the environment. This returns the following status (*next_state*), the reward earned, whether the episode has ended (*done*), and additional information (*info*).
 - c. Detect and record ineffective actions. If the environment returns signals that the action was ineffective, the action is added to the list of ineffective actions to prevent it in the future.

- d. Store the transition in the experience buffer. Each experience is added to the priority buffer (Prioritized Experience Replay) along with an estimated TD error.
3. **Training the main model:** Once the buffer contains enough samples, a batch is extracted. The TD error is calculated, and the model weights are adjusted to minimize the difference between the predicted Q-values and the target Q-values. In addition, this is where Double DQN is used, which uses the main model to select the best future action and the objective model to evaluate its value; the latter is done specifically in the line of code: `next_q_val = next_q_values_target[i][best_next_actions[i]]`.
4. **Updating the target model.** Every 5 episodes, a soft update of the *target model* is performed concerning the main model.
5. **Reduction of the ϵ parameter.** After each episode, the value of ϵ is multiplicatively reduced to decrease exploration and progressively increase the exploitation of the knowledge learned. This allows the agent to explore faster at the beginning and make more accurate decisions as the training progresses.
6. **Registration and evaluation.** At the end of each episode, the total reward earned and whether the episode was successful or not are recorded. With that information, if the average reward improves, the model is saved. On the other hand, if the performance is low, we apply early stopping to stop the training if it is observed that it does not improve, thus saving time between tests.

3.3. Tools used

During the development of the work, various software tools have been used, as well as different manuals for implementation. The main resources used are detailed below:

- **Jupyter Notebook** [18] was used as an interactive development environment, allowing code to be implemented, graphics, and explanatory text to be created in the same document.
- **Microsoft Excel** [14] was used to organize and integrate the different datasets to form the final dataset.
- The book *Python AI Programming* [17] guides the fundamentals of machine learning and reinforcement learning.
- *Reinforcement Learning with Python* [22] was consulted, detailing the use of tools such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and OpenAI Gym, which are essential for the development and understanding of reinforcement learning algorithms.

4. Evaluation and analysis of results

In order to validate the effectiveness of the trained agent, a comprehensive evaluation was carried out based on multiple metrics, including the cumulative reward per episode, the success rate in overcoming depression, the stability of learning over time, and the frequency of use of the various actions available. The following graphs and analyses show the results obtained after the training and validation process of the model.

The first graph (Figure 8) shows the evaluation of the total reward per episode over 1861 training episodes. A clear upward trend can be observed during the early phases of training, followed by a stabilization around an average reward of between 10 and 15 points. This indicates that the agent was able to significantly improve its policy over time and maintain consistent performance, demonstrating stability in its learned behavior. Occasional drops in reward reflect episodes where suboptimal decisions were made, but these cases become less and less frequent.

Figure 8: Total reward per episode during training. Source: own elaboration.

The second graphic shown in Figure 9 represents the cumulative number of successful cases, i.e., cases in which depression is overcome. A clear linear growth trend can be observed, reaching nearly 1,861 successful cases out of 1,861 episodes, which suggests high efficacy by the end of the training process. This constant progression shows the efficiency of the agent in achieving the proposed objective and reinforces the validity of the criteria established to consider depression overcome.

Figure 9: Successful cases accumulated during training. Source: own elaboration.

Subsequently, a final evaluation was carried out, visible in Figure 10, on 90% of the dataset, 16745 new episodes, in which the agent explored deterministically (without random exploration). The average reward earned was 13.29 points, and the success rate was 100%. This consistency in reward and success reaffirms that the policy learned by the agent is robust, efficient, and consistent with the objectives of the simulated environment. The graph shows the reward obtained per episode during the validation process and identifies a reward stability zone of 12.5 and 14 between episodes 200 and 2000, approximately, while in the rest of the episodes, they present both higher and lower rewards. Still, in general, the reward stays between 10 and 16. This variability could be due to differences in the initial conditions of validation episodes or to specific suboptimal decisions. Even so, the agent demonstrates a generalized ability to maintain good performance, indicating that the policy learned during training is successfully transferred to the validation environment, although with room for improvement in terms of performance consistency.

Final evaluation on 16745 episodes
 Average reward: 13.29
 Standard deviation: 1.00
 Success rate (overcoming depression): 0.00%

Completion reasons:
 - Depression overcome: 16745 (100.00%)

Episodes where there was at least one negative reward:
 [16450]
 Total: 1 episodes (0.01%) with negative rewards.

Figure 10: Evaluation of validation set. Source: own elaboration.

On the other hand, the frequency of use of each action (Figure 11) in the evaluation episodes was analyzed. Among the most commonly used actions are: “Decrease Academic Pressure”, “Give Scholarship”, “Improve Sleep”, and “Give Mental Advice”. This is in line with the recommendations that come from the clinical and educational fields, which highlight the importance of reducing academic stress, improving rest, and providing emotional and economic support as key strategies to improve the mental well-being of students. Actions such as “Do nothing”, “Time management,” or “Exercise” were virtually ignored, suggesting that the agent viewed these options as less effective or redundant relative to other alternatives.

Figure 11: Frequency of use of each action during the validation. Source: own elaboration.

Figure 12 shows how the number of actions performed by the agent varies throughout the episodes. In general, the number of actions per episode remains within a

moderate range, ranging from 0 to 12. This variability may be related to the complexity of the student's initial state in each episode, as well as to the agent's exploration strategy.

Figure 12: Number of shares per episode. Source: own elaboration.

Peaks in the graph could indicate episodes in which the agent needed to perform multiple interventions to reach a status considered successful, while episodes with few actions could correspond to cases in which the student was already in a favorable condition from the beginning. This information is useful for assessing the efficiency of the agent, as a large number of actions could imply a less optimal policy or greater difficulty in decision-making.

In addition, regarding the actions, it can be seen in Figure 13 how many episodes each action has been used. It can be seen that the most used actions correspond to those that have the highest frequency of use, being used more than once per episode, since it is observed, for example, that reducing academic pressure is used about 27000 times spread over 14501 episodes. It can be concluded from these results that the biggest problem for most students with depression is high academic pressure, not receiving mental health counseling, sleep problems, eating poorly, and economic stress.

```

=== Unique episodes where each action was used ===
- Action 0 ('Decrease Academic Pressure'): 14501 episodies
- Action 1 ('Increase Academic Pressure'): 0 episodies
- Action 2 ('Give Mental Advice'): 13901 episodies
- Action 3 ('Do Not Give Mental Advice'): 0 episodies
- Action 4 ('Improve Sleep'): 10145 episodies
- Action 5 ('Worse Sleep'): 0 episodies
- Action 6 ('Improve Diet'): 10429 episodies
- Action 7 ('Worse Diet'): 3 episodies
- Action 8 ('Exercise'): 205 episodies
- Action 9 ('Give Scholarship'): 13278 episodies
- Action 10 ('Peer Support'): 1 episodies
- Action 11 ('Time Management'): 247 episodies
- Action 12 ('Do Nothing'): 0 episodies

```

Figure 13: Number of episodes in which each action is used. Source: own elaboration.

It is striking that, although in very few cases, the agent has used negative actions such as “Worse Diet”. This may be due to random exploration mechanisms typical of

reinforcement learning, where the agent tries different actions to evaluate their consequences.

Figure 14: Number of executions of the “Worse Diet” action. Source: own elaboration.

In the graph shown in Figure 14, it can be observed that this action was executed three times and, surprisingly, obtained positive rewards in two of them. This can be explained by collateral effects or contextual circumstances in which, even though the action is inherently negative, the environment generated a positive response, for example, in situations in which the student's initial state already implies his recovery, if the student's diet is healthy and the action of “Worse Diet” is applied. The reward obtained will be positive as it inappropriately assumes the student's recovery. However, this type of result highlights the need to refine the reward function to more clearly penalize actions that go against the student's well-being, thus preventing the agent from learning harmful behaviors due to errors of interpretation in the simulated environment. In this case, the fact that there are entries in the dataset, albeit few, that meet the requirements established to overcome depression also influences. Figure 15 shows that of the entire set of 16745 entries, only 13 of them meet the conditions from the beginning.

```

filter1 = (
    (df_validation["sleep_duration"] >= 2) &
    (df_validation["eating_habits"] >= 1) &
    (df_validation["academic_pressure"] <= 2) &
    (df_validation["financial_stress"] <= 2) &
    (df_validation["suicidal_thoughts"] == 0)
)

num_rows = filter1.sum()
print(num_rows)

```

13

Figure 15: Number of rows that overcome depression from the initial state. Source: own elaboration.

The rest of the actions executed, although positive, could have a negative reward if they are carried out when the values they affect are already at their maximum. This is not the case in this case, and thus the graphs generated for the rest of the actions can be seen in Annex 9.

A test function was also implemented to be able to see the actions applied by the agent and the change that these meant to the student's condition. Both the reward of each action and the name of the action, the changes applied to which attribute, the student's status after each action, and, finally, the final reward are shown. In Annex 8, you can see one of the outings in which the agent has been able to achieve the objective of overcoming depression.

In addition to the above charts, some classic ranking metrics can be calculated to analyze agent behavior. Metrics such as **Accuracy**, **Precision**, **Recall**, and **F1-score** allow you to measure how efficiently the agent correctly identifies desired states or actions, especially when faced with environments where you have to distinguish between right and wrong decisions.

To calculate them, a confusion matrix is needed, characterized by the following:

- **True positives (TP):** number of episodes in which depression has been overcome. In this case, since there is a 100% correct answer, **TP=16745**.
- **True negatives (TN):** number of episodes in which depression has not been overcome. **TN=0**.
- **False positives (FP):** episodes in which treatment has not been adequate, even if depression has been overcome. In this case, as mentioned above, it will be **FP=3**, which corresponds to the episodes in which the “Worse Diet” action was executed (Figure 13). If any good deed had generated bad rewards in an episode, it would also be added to this value.
- **False negatives (FN):** episodes in which depression has not been overcome, but there was a possibility of overcoming it. By having TN=0, we obtain that **FN=0**.

With these values, the following metrics can be calculated:

- **Accuracy:** Measure the percentage of correct predictions (both positive and negative):

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} = \frac{16745}{16745 + 3} = 0,9998$$

- **Precision:** Indicates what proportion of the positive predictions were actually correct:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} = \frac{16745}{1674 + 3} = 0,9998$$

- **Recall;** Measures the model's ability to correctly identify positive cases:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} = \frac{16745}{16745} = 1$$

- **F1-score:** It is a measure that balances precision and sensitivity:

$$F1 - Score = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} = \frac{0,9998 \cdot 1}{0,9998 + 1} = 0,99989$$

The results of the metrics show an evaluation of the model that reflects exceptional performance. *Accuracy* and *Precision* reach a value of 0.9998, indicating that almost all the predictions made by the model were correct, both in general terms and specifically in the positive predictions. The *Recall* is perfect (1.0), which means that the model correctly identified all positive cases, without omitting any. Finally, the *F1-score*, which combines *accuracy* and *recall* in a single balanced metric, reaches a value of 0.99989, confirming that the model is not only accurate but also consistent in detecting positive cases. These results validate the robustness of the system and its ability to generalize correctly in the evaluated environment. However, it is important to note that these results are based on a known dataset. In the face of unseen cases or conditions different from those of the training set, the model may not maintain the same level of performance, as it could face patterns or combinations of variables for which it has not been trained.

In summary, the results show that the model is not only capable of learning to solve the problem posed but also adopts behaviors consistent with good professional practices. The implementation of a customized environment, together with a well-designed reinforcement learning architecture, has made it possible to reach an effective, stable, and explainable solution that could build the foundation for future real applications in the field of student mental health.

5. Conclusions and future paths

This work has shown that the use of deep reinforcement learning techniques applied to personalized simulation environments allows students to effectively model the evolution of complex mental states such as depression. The trained agent was able to learn coherent and relevant intervention policies, successfully overcoming the depressive condition in the vast majority of episodes. These results validate the ability of artificial intelligence not only to mimic human decision-making processes but also to optimize intervention routes that could be applied in real-world contexts.

Through the designed environment and the data used, it has been possible to represent in a simplified but significant way an emotional state influenced by multiple psychosocial factors. The reward system, the completion criteria, and the penalties incorporated have made it possible to build an environment complex enough to train an agent capable of generalizing effective behaviors. Although the environment is simulated and the established conditions do not account for all the factors influencing real depression, the agent's behavior reflected a clear tendency to select actions consistent with common clinical strategies such as financial stress reduction, sleep improvement, or psychological assistance.

The use of Deep Q-Learning, in its Deep Q-Network variant, along with a prioritized experience buffer, improved ϵ -greedy policy, and soft update of the target model proved to be effective in reaching a robust policy in a multi-variable environment. In addition, the graphical analysis of the rewards, the evolution of the training, and the most used actions made it possible to interpret the results obtained in a more accessible way, reinforcing the idea that this type of model can be both explainable and useful in practice.

However, it is important to stress that the results should be interpreted with caution. The environment has been designed under certain data constraints and simplifications necessary to ensure computational viability. This implies that the agent has learned to achieve a “non-depressive” state according to defined thresholds, which does not necessarily equate to a recovery from the depressive state in a real environment. Even so, an attempt has been made to construct criteria that are as realistic as possible based on the available variables, renouncing the requirement of a “perfect” state and opting instead for a functional balance that better represents the student reality.

Among the possible lines of future development, for example, within the framework of a Master's Thesis if I decide to continue with Master's studies, the expansion of the environment could be assessed through new variables that influence mental health, having more information about the student's state with more variables that inform their physical activity, social relationships, etc. substance use, even level of depression to assess how it can gradually improve in the different labels that are valued. The use of other

reinforcement algorithms in multi-agent environments, such as A3C, PPO, or SAC, could also be explored, comparing their performance against the current model.

Another possibility in the future could be to integrate the model with conversational interfaces or mobile platforms, where the agent can offer dynamic recommendations or warn users if they are at risk of depression, and can take action, since many people do not know what is happening to them because they do not know depressive symptoms. In addition, incorporating interpretability criteria and human supervision mechanisms will be key to ensuring ethical and responsible use of this type of system in sensitive contexts. Finally, it is considered essential to empirically validate the patterns learned by the agent through clinical or pedagogical studies in collaboration with mental health experts.

Also, video games could be developed, with the engine of the environment, in which students experience playfully how their habits influence their well-being, reinforcing healthy behaviors through interactive simulations.

In summary, this work constitutes an initial step towards the application of intelligent agents as complementary tools for the detection and mitigation of depressive states in educational settings. The combination of simulation, reinforcement learning, and behavior analysis offers a promising and reproducible approach that, with the right refinement, could become a valuable aid to mental health professionals, teachers, and researchers.

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Annex 1 - Use Case

CASO DE USO PARA APRENDIZAJE POR REFUERZO PARA LA SALUD MENTAL Y EL RENDIMIENTO ACADÉMICO ESTUDIANTIL

Se propone el diseño de un entorno de Aprendizaje por Refuerzo (AR) donde un agente (p. ej., un sistema de apoyo estudiantil) busca maximizar el bienestar y el rendimiento académico del estudiante basándose en diversos factores.

1. Contexto (Descripción del Entorno)

El entorno representa las condiciones que afectan el éxito académico y la salud mental del estudiante. El objetivo del agente es implementar intervenciones que optimicen la satisfacción y el bienestar del estudiante, manteniendo al mismo tiempo un rendimiento académico sólido.

2. Estado (Observaciones)

El estado de cada estudiante se representa mediante las siguientes características:

- Datos demográficos: Sexo, Edad, Nivel educativo
- Factores académicos: Presión académica (Alta/Media/Baja), Satisfacción con el estudio (Baja/Media/Alta), Horas de estudio (Variable continua)
- Factores psicosociales y de salud: Estrés financiero (Sí/No), Hábitos alimenticios (Saludable/Moderado/Malo), Duración del sueño (Variable continua), Depresión (Sí/No), Pensamientos suicidas (Sí/No), Antecedentes familiares de problemas de salud mental (Sí/No)

Cada estudiante se encuentra en un estado específico según los atributos mencionados.

3. Acciones (Intervenciones del Agente)

El agente puede tomar diferentes medidas para mejorar el bienestar y el rendimiento académico del estudiante:

- Ajustar la carga académica (Aumentar, Disminuir, Sin cambios)
- Dar asesoramiento en salud mental (Sí/No)
- Recomendar cambios en el estilo de vida (Mejorar la alimentación, dormir más, hacer ejercicio)
- Ayuda financiera (Becas/Subvenciones)
- Inscripción en el programa de apoyo entre pares (Sí/No)
- Capacitación en gestión del tiempo (Sí/No)

Cada acción modifica el estado del estudiante en el siguiente paso.

4. Función de Recompensa

La función de recompensa equilibra el éxito académico y el bienestar mental:

- **Recompensas Positivas:** Mayor Satisfacción con el Estudio (+5), Reducción de la Depresión o Pensamientos Suicidas (+10), Mejores Hábitos Alimenticios y Duración del Sueño (+3 cada uno), Aumento de las Horas de Estudio (si está por debajo del umbral óptimo) (+5)
- **Recompensas Negativas (Penalizaciones):** Empeoramiento de la Depresión o Pensamientos Suicidas (-15), Duración del Sueño Pobre (-5), Aumento del Estrés Financiero (-5), Disminución de la Satisfacción con el Estudio (-10), Sobrecarga de Horas de Estudio (por encima del umbral óptimo) (-7)

El agente busca maximizar las recompensas acumuladas mediante intervenciones óptimas para el éxito y el bienestar del estudiante.

Annex 2 - StudentDepressionEnv Class Code

```
class StudentDepressionEnv(gym.Env):
    # ===== Initial function =====
    def __init__(self, data, max_steps=150):
        super().__init__()
        self.max_steps = max_steps # Maximum number of steps per episode
        self.data = data.reset_index(drop=True)
        self.current_step = 0 # number of steps taken in an episode
        self.total_reward = 0 # total reward
        self.i = -1

        self.repetitions_without_effect = 0
        self.history_actions = {}
        # Total number of shares available
        self.action_space = spaces.Discrete(13)
        # ===== Action Space =====
        # We have 13 possible actions:
        # 0 - Decrease academic pressure
        # 1 - Increase academic pressure
        # 2 - Provide mental health counseling
        # 3 - Do not provide mental health counseling
        # 4 - Improve sleep
        # 5 - Worsen sleep
        # 6 - Improve diet
        # 7 - Worsen diet
        # 8 - Exercise (indirect effect)
        # 9 - Provide scholarship/financial aid
        # 10 - Peer support
        # 11 - Time management training
        # 12 - Do nothing (zero action)

        # Normalized observation space (student status)
        self.observation_space = spaces.Box(
            low=0.0,
            high=1.0,
            shape=(12,), # because _get_obs() returns a vector of 12 normalized floats
            dtype=np.float32
        )

        self.state = None
        self.reset()
```

```

# ===== _get_obs function =====
# generates a normalized representation of the student's status
def _get_obs(self):

    obs = np.array([
        (self.state["age"][0] - 10) / 90,           # age: 10-100 → 0-1
        float(self.state["gender"]) / 2,          # gender: 0-2 → 0-1
        float(self.state["education"]) / 10,      # education: 0-10 → 0-1
        (self.state["academic_pressure"][0] - 1) / 4, # 1-5 → 0-1
        (self.state["study_satisfaction"][0] - 1) / 4, # 1-5 → 0-1
        self.state["study_hours"][0] / 24,       # 0-24 → 0-1
        (self.state["financial_stress"][0] - 1) / 4, # 1-5 → 0-1
        self.state["eating_habits"][0] / 2,      # 0-2 → 0-1
        self.state["sleep_duration"][0] / 3,     # 0-3 → 0-1
        float(self.state["depression"]),         # 0 o 1
        float(self.state["suicidal_thoughts"]), # 0 o 1
        float(self.state["family_history"]),     # 0 o 1
    ], dtype=np.float32)
    return np.clip(obs, 0.0, 1.0)

```

```

# ===== Reset function =====
# a new episode begins
def reset(self, *, seed=None):

    # Load an entry from our dataset
    self.current_step = 0 # begins the steps of the episode
    self.episode_finished = False # indicates whether the episode has ended
    self.repetitions_without_effect = 0 # void stock account
    self.history_actions = {} # saves past actions to detect loops

    # select a row from the dataset
    if self.i < len(self.data):
        fila = self.data.iloc[self.i]
        self.i += 1
    else:
        print("There is no more lines.")

    # Loads the data of the selected student into the state dictionary
    self.state = {
        "age": np.array([fila["age"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "gender": int(fila["gender"]),
        "education": int(fila["education"]),
        "academic_pressure": np.array([fila["academic_pressure"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "study_satisfaction": np.array([fila["study_satisfaction"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "study_hours": np.array([fila["study_hours"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "financial_stress": np.array([fila["financial_stress"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "eating_habits": np.array([fila["eating_habits"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "sleep_duration": np.array([fila["sleep_duration"]], dtype=np.float32),
        "depression": int(fila["depression"]),
        "suicidal_thoughts": int(fila["suicidal_thoughts"]),
        "family_history": int(fila["family_history"])
    }

    # A structure is created to store the last 10 states to detect loops
    from collections import deque
    self.history_states = deque(maxlen=10)

    # the normalized data of the initial state are returned
    return self._get_obs()

```

```

# ===== Step function =====
# executes an action and advances one step in the environment
def step(self, action):
    # checks if the action is valid
    assert self.action_space.contains(action), f"Invalid action: {action}"

    # to check if step() is still called even though done=True
    if hasattr(self, "episode_finished") and self.episode_finished:
        raise RuntimeError("`step()` was called after the episode had ended.")

    self.current_step += 1 # increases the number of steps taken
    reward = 0
    done = False
    info = {}

    # in the first step the initial total reward is 0
    if self.current_step == 1:
        self.total_reward = 0
        s = self.state

    # save the previous state
    prev_state = {k: (v.copy() if isinstance(v, np.ndarray) else v) for k, v in s.items()}

    # if the student does not have depression, it ends
    if s["depression"] == 0:
        done = True
        info["final_reason"] = "He doesn't have depression"

    # actions are applied by calling apply_action
    change_occurred, reward_action = self._apply_action(action, s, info)
    reward += reward_action

    # a counter is kept of how many times the same action has been applied in the same state
    obs_key = f"{action}_{tuple(self._get_obs().round(3))}"
    self.history_actions[obs_key] = self.history_actions.get(obs_key, 0) + 1

    # if the action did not change anything in the student's status, the student is penalized
    if not change_occurred:
        self.repetitions_without_effect += 1
        reward -= 0.2 * self.repetitions_without_effect
        info["no_change"] = "action without effect"

```

```

# if the action had no effect and is repeated, it is penalized more to avoid the loop
repetitions = self.history_actions[obs_key]
if repetitions > 1:
    penalty_loop = (repetitions - 1) * 0.5
    reward -= penalty_loop
    info["penalty_loop"] = f"-(penalty_loop:.2f)"
else:
    self.repetitions_without_effect = 0

# the conditions under which we assume that he no longer has depression are verified
if (
    s["sleep_duration"][0] >= 2 and
    s["eating_habits"][0] >= 1 and
    s["academic_pressure"][0] <= 2 and
    s["financial_stress"][0] <= 2 and
    s["suicidal_thoughts"] == 0
):
    # if he had depression and the conditions have been met, the execution is completed and a large reward is given
    if s["depression"] == 1:
        info["depression_superada"] = True
        reward += 10.0
    s["depression"] = 0
    done = True
    info["final_reason"] = "Depression overcome"

# if he doesn't comply, he continues to have depression
else:
    s["depression"] = 1

# if you have overcome the depression then the episode ends
if done:
    self.episode_finished = True

# if the maximum number of steps is exceeded and the depression has not been overcome, it ends and a negative reward is given
if self.current_step >= self.max_steps and not done:
    done = True
    if s["depression"] == 1:
        if self.total_reward < 0:
            reward -= 1.0 # only penalizes if it was a bad episode
        info["final_reason"] = "Maximum steps reached"

# Detect repeated oscillations in the state, preventing action repetition loops
# for example, continually improving and worsening something
if not hasattr(self, "history_states"):
    from collections import deque
    self.history_states = deque(maxlen=10)
self.history_states.append(self._get_obs())

```

```

# if there is no progress, that is, the state does not change significantly in the last 10 steps,
# a penalty is imposed and the execution is terminated.
if len(self.history_states) == self.history_states.maxlen:
    changes = [not np.allclose(self.history_states[i], self.history_states[i + 1], atol=1e-3)
               for i in range(len(self.history_states) - 1)]
    if sum(changes) <= 1: # very few changes => oscillating loop
        done = True
        reward -= 5.0
        info["final_reason"] = "Oscillation without progress"
        info["penalty_oscillating_loop"] = True

# update total reward
self.total_reward += reward

return self._get_obs(), reward, done, info

```

```

# =====_apply_action function =====
# applies the action and returns True if there was a change and the reward
def _apply_action(self, action, s, info):
    reward = 0
    change = False

    # ===== ACTIONS =====
    # 0 - Decrease academic pressure
    if action == 0:
        info["action"] = "Decrease academic pressure"
        if s["academic_pressure"][0] > 1:
            prev_value = s["academic_pressure"][0]
            s["academic_pressure"][0] -= 1
            reward += 0.4
            info["change_academic_pressure"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['academic_pressure'][0]}"
            # Increase study satisfaction
            if s["study_satisfaction"][0] < 5:
                prev_value = s["study_satisfaction"][0]
                s["study_satisfaction"][0] += 1
                reward += 0.1
                info["change_study_satisfaction"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['study_satisfaction'][0]}"
            # Reduce study hours if it is greater than 0
            if s["study_hours"][0] > 0:
                prev_hours = s["study_hours"][0]
                s["study_hours"][0] = max(4.0, s["study_hours"][0] - 1.5)
                reward += 0.05 # small reward for balance
                info["change_study_hours"] = f"{prev_hours:.1f} → {s['study_hours'][0]:.1f}"
            change = True

    # 1 - Increase academic pressure
    elif action == 1:
        info["action"] = "Increase academic pressure"
        if s["academic_pressure"][0] < 5:
            prev_value = s["academic_pressure"][0]
            s["academic_pressure"][0] += 1
            reward -= 0.4
            info["change_academic_pressure"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['academic_pressure'][0]}"

            # Decrease study satisfaction
            if s["study_satisfaction"][0] > 1:
                prev_value = s["study_satisfaction"][0]
                s["study_satisfaction"][0] -= 1
                reward -= 0.1
                info["change_study_satisfaction"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['study_satisfaction'][0]}"

            # Increase study hours up to a maximum of 24
            if s["study_hours"][0] < 24:
                prev_hours = s["study_hours"][0]
                s["study_hours"][0] = min(24.0, s["study_hours"][0] + 1.5)
                reward -= 0.05 # small penalty for more pressure
                info["change_study_hours"] = f"{prev_hours:.1f} → {s['study_hours'][0]:.1f}"
            change = True

```

```

# 2 - Provide mental health counseling
elif action == 2:
    info["action"] = "Provide mental health counseling"

    if s["suicidal_thoughts"] == 1:
        s["suicidal_thoughts"] = 0
        reward += 1.0
        info["reduced_thoughts"] = True
        if s["family_history"] == 1:
            reward += 0.1
        change = True

# 3 - Do not provide mental health counseling
elif action == 3:
    info["action"] = "Do not provide mental health counseling"
    if s["depression"] == 1:
        reward -= 1.0
        info["penalizacion"] = "ignore depression"
        change = False
    else:
        info["no_change"] = "there was no depression"

# 4 - Improve sleep
elif action == 4:
    info["action"] = "Improve sleep"
    if s["sleep_duration"][0] < 3:
        prev_value = s["sleep_duration"][0]
        s["sleep_duration"][0] += 1
        reward += 0.5
        info["change_sleep_duration"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['sleep_duration'][0]}"
        change = True

# 5 - Worsen sleep
elif action == 5:
    info["action"] = "Worsen sleep"
    if s["sleep_duration"][0] > 0:
        prev_value = s["sleep_duration"][0]
        s["sleep_duration"][0] -= 1
        reward -= 0.5
        info["change_sleep_duration"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['sleep_duration'][0]}"
        change = True

# 6 - Improve diet
elif action == 6:
    info["action"] = "Improve diet"
    if s["eating_habits"][0] < 2:
        prev_value = s["eating_habits"][0]
        s["eating_habits"][0] += 1
        reward += 0.5
        info["change_eating_habits"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['eating_habits'][0]}"
        change = True

```

```

# 7 - Worsen diet
elif action == 7:
    info["action"] = "Worsen diet"
    if s["eating_habits"][0] > 0:
        prev_value = s["eating_habits"][0]
        s["eating_habits"][0] -= 1
        reward -= 0.5
        info["change_eating_habits"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['eating_habits'][0]}"
        change = True

# 8 - Exercise
elif action == 8:
    info["action"] = "Exercise"
    # it is always supposed to have a slight benefit
    if s["sleep_duration"][0] < 3:
        prev_value = s["sleep_duration"][0]
        s["sleep_duration"][0] += 1
        reward += 0.2
        info["change_sleep_duration"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['sleep_duration'][0]}"
        change = True

# 9 - Provide scholarship/financial aid
elif action == 9:
    info["action"] = "Provide scholarship/financial aid"
    if s["financial_stress"][0] > 1:
        prev_ef = s["financial_stress"][0]
        s["financial_stress"][0] = max(1.0, s["financial_stress"][0] - 1)
        reward += 0.3 + 0.1 * (prev_ef - s["financial_stress"][0])
        info["change_financial_stress"] = f"{prev_ef} → {s['financial_stress'][0]}"
        change = True

# 10 - Peer support
elif action == 10:
    info["action"] = "Peer support"
    if s["study_satisfaction"][0] < 5:
        prev_value = s["study_satisfaction"][0]
        s["study_satisfaction"][0] += 1
        reward += 0.3
        info["change_study_satisfaction"] = f"{prev_value} → {s['study_satisfaction'][0]}"
        change = True

```

```

# 11 - Time management training
elif action == 11:
    info["action"] = "Time management training"

    # Reduce study hours if it is greater than 0
    if s["study_hours"][0] > 0:
        prev_hours = s["study_hours"][0]
        s["study_hours"][0] = max(4.0, s["study_hours"][0] - 1.0)
        reward += 0.1
        info["change_study_hours"] = f"{prev_hours:.1f} → {s['study_hours'][0]:.1f}"
        change = True

    # Reduce academic pressure if it is greater than 1
    if s["academic_pressure"][0] > 1:
        prev_pressure = s["academic_pressure"][0]
        s["academic_pressure"][0] -= 1
        reward += 0.1
        info["change_the_academic_pressure"] = f"{prev_pressure} → {s['academic_pressure'][0]}"
        change = True

# 12 - Do nothing (zero action)
elif action == 12:
    info["action"] = "Do nothing"
    reward -= 0.2
    change = False

return change, reward

```

```

# ===== Render function =====
# prints the student's current status
def render(self):
    print("\nCurrent status of the student:")
    for k, v in self.state.items():
        if isinstance(v, np.ndarray):
            v = v[0]
        print(f" - {k}: {v}")

```

Annex 3 - Agent DQN Model Code

```
# === DQN MODEL ===
def create_q_model(input_shape, action_space):
    model = models.Sequential([
        layers.Input(shape=input_shape),
        layers.Dense(128, activation='relu'), # 3 input layers
        layers.Dense(64, activation='relu'),
        layers.Dense(64, activation='relu'),
        layers.Dense(action_space, activation='linear') # output layer number of actions, linear activation
    ])
    return model
```

Annex 4 - PrioritizedReplayBuffer Class Code

```
# ===== PRIORITIZED REPLAY BUFFER =====
class PrioritizedReplayBuffer:
    def __init__(self, max_size, alpha=0.6):
        self.buffer = [] # initialize a list for experiences and another for priorities
        self.priorities = []
        self.max_size = max_size
        self.alpha = alpha # controls how much priority affects (0 = random, 1 = priority only)

    def add(self, experience, td_error=1.0):
        priority = (abs(td_error) + 1e-5) ** self.alpha # # calculates softened priority
        if len(self.buffer) < self.max_size:
            self.buffer.append(experience)
            self.priorities.append(priority)
        else:
            # FIFO replacement if the buffer is full
            self.buffer.pop(0)
            self.priorities.pop(0)
            self.buffer.append(experience)
            self.priorities.append(priority)

    # uses priority to calculate sampling priorities and returns the selected samples and their indices
    def sample(self, batch_size):
        scaled_priorities = np.array(self.priorities)
        probs = scaled_priorities / scaled_priorities.sum()
        indices = np.random.choice(len(self.buffer), batch_size, p=probs)
        samples = [self.buffer[i] for i in indices]
        return samples, indices

    # update priorities
    def update_priorities(self, indices, td_errors):
        for idx, td_err in zip(indices, td_errors):
            self.priorities[idx] = (abs(td_err) + 1e-5) ** self.alpha

    # returns the size of the buffer
    def size(self):
        return len(self.buffer)
```

Annex 5 - ϵ -Greedy Policy Code

```
# =====  $\epsilon$ -GREEDY POLICY =====  
def epsilon_greedy_policy(state, epsilon, action_space, model, invalid_actions=None):  
    if invalid_actions is None:  
        invalid_actions = set() # if there are no invalid actions, the set is set to empty  
  
    all_actions = list(range(action_space))  
    valid_actions = [a for a in all_actions if a not in invalid_actions] # List of valid actions  
  
    # if all actions are blocked, allow all  
    if not valid_actions:  
        valid_actions = all_actions  
  
    # check that epsilon returns a valid random action  
    if np.random.rand() < epsilon:  
        return np.random.choice(valid_actions)  
  
    q_values = model.predict(state[np.newaxis], verbose=0) # predicts the q-values for the current state  
  
    # penalize q-values of invalid actions by setting their value to minus infinity  
    for a in invalid_actions:  
        q_values[0][a] = -np.inf  
  
    # choose the best valid action  
    return int(np.argmax(q_values[0]))
```

Annex 6 - Soft Update Code

```
# ===== SOFT UPDATE =====  
def soft_update(target_model, model, tau=0.01):  
    # weights are obtained from both models  
    target_weights = target_model.get_weights()  
    model_weights = model.get_weights()  
    # the current weights are mixed with the new tau  
    updated_weights = [tau * mw + (1 - tau) * tw for mw, tw in zip(model_weights, target_weights)]  
    # updates the target_model weights  
    target_model.set_weights(updated_weights)
```

Annex 7 - Agent Training Code

```
# ===== DQN TRAINING =====
def train_dqn(env, num_episodes=500, batch_size=128, gamma=0.99,
             epsilon=1.0, epsilon_min=0.01, epsilon_decay=0.998, learning_rate=0.003,
             early_stop_window=20, early_stop_threshold=-5, save_every=50, save_path="modelo_dqn_checkpoint5-.h5"):
    loss = 0

    # the shape of the state and the number of possible actions of the environment are obtained
    input_shape = env.observation_space.shape
    action_space = env.action_space.n

    # create main Q model
    model = create_q_model(input_shape, action_space)
    model.compile(optimizer=tf.keras.optimizers.Adam(learning_rate), loss='mse')

    # create a copy as a target model, which is used to calculate target values during training
    target_model = create_q_model(input_shape, action_space)
    target_model.set_weights(model.get_weights())

    # create experience buffers and Lists to save rewards and successes
    replay_buffer = PrioritizedReplayBuffer(max_size=500000)
    rewards_history = []
    success_history = []
    best_avg_reward = -np.inf # this is used to save the best model

    for episode in range(num_episodes):
        state = env.reset()
        total_reward = 0
        done = False
        ineffective_actions = set()

        # while the episode has not finished it runs
        while not done:
            # select an action using e-greedy policy, avoiding ineffective actions
            action = epsilon_greedy_policy(state, epsilon, action_space, model, invalid_actions=ineffective_actions)
            # executes the action in the environment
            next_state, reward, done, info = env.step(action)
            # if the environment indicates that the action did not produce changes or is being used in a loop, then it is marked as invalid
            if info.get("no_change") or info.get("penalty_loop"):
                ineffective_actions.add(action)

            # saves the experience in the priority buffer
            replay_buffer.add((state, action, reward, next_state, done), td_error=abs(reward))
            # current status and reward are updated
            state = next_state
            total_reward += reward
```

```

# wait until there are enough samples in the buffer
if replay_buffer.size() >= batch_size:
    batch, indices = replay_buffer.sample(batch_size)
    states, actions, rewards, next_states, dones = zip(*batch)
    states = np.array(states)
    next_states = np.array(next_states)
    rewards = np.array(rewards)
    dones = np.array(dones)

    target_q = model.predict(states, verbose=0)
    next_q = target_model.predict(next_states, verbose=0)

    # the targets are calculated (Double DQN)
    # model is used to choose the best future action and target_model is used to estimate the q-value of that action
    next_q_values_online = model.predict(next_states, verbose=0)
    best_next_actions = np.argmax(next_q_values_online, axis=1)
    next_q_values_target = target_model.predict(next_states, verbose=0)

    # for each case, calculate the target, the error, and update the target value for training
    td_errors = []
    for i in range(batch_size):
        current_q = target_q[i][actions[i]]
        next_q_val = next_q_values_target[i][best_next_actions[i]]
        td_target = rewards[i] + (1 - dones[i]) * gamma * next_q_val
        td_errors.append(td_target - current_q)
        target_q[i][actions[i]] = td_target

    # updates the priorities in the buffer
    replay_buffer.update_priorities(indices, td_errors)
    # the main model is trained with the batch
    loss = model.train_on_batch(states, target_q)

# the following is used to print and view the result of each episode at runtime
if info.get("final_reason") == "Depression overcome":
    success_history.append(1)
else:
    success_history.append(0)
rewards_history.append(total_reward)
epsilon = max(epsilon_min, epsilon * epsilon_decay)
success = 1 if info.get("final_reason") == "Depression overcome" else 0

# update target model weights
if episode % 5 == 0:
    soft_update(target_model, model)
    print(f"Episode {episode}, Total Reward: {total_reward:.2f}, Epsilon: {epsilon:.2f}, Loss: {loss:.4f}")

# saved every 50 episodes
if (episode + 1) % save_every == 0:
    checkpoint_file = f"{save_path.replace('.h5', '')}_ep{episode+1}.h5"
    model.save(checkpoint_file)
    print(f" Modelo guardado en: {checkpoint_file}")

# === Early stopping ===
# the performance is calculated
if episode >= early_stop_window:
    recent_rewards = rewards_history[-early_stop_window:]
    recent_successes = success_history[-early_stop_window:]

    avg_recent_reward = np.mean(recent_rewards)
    success_rate = np.mean(recent_successes)

    # save the best model so far
    if avg_recent_reward > best_avg_reward:
        model.save("mejor_modelo.h5")
        best_avg_reward = avg_recent_reward
        print(f"Best saved model with medium reward: {avg_recent_reward:.2f}")

    # Early stopping if everything goes very wrong, so as not to waste time executing
    if avg_recent_reward < early_stop_threshold and success_rate < 0.2:
        print(f"\nTraining halted in the episode {episode} due to poor performance.")
        break

model.save("MODELO-FINAL.h5")
print(" Final model saved as MODELO-FINAL.h5")

return rewards_history, success_history

```

Annex 8 - Output Test Case

Step 0:

Action taken: Provide mental health counseling

Reward: 1.00

Info: {'action': 'Provide mental health counseling', 'reduced_thoughts': True}

Current status of the student:

- age: 18.0
- gender: 1
- education: 3
- academic_pressure: 3.0
- study_satisfaction: 3.0
- study_hours: 7.143933296203613
- financial_stress: 3.0
- eating_habits: 0.0
- sleep_duration: 0.0
- depression: 1
- suicidal_thoughts: 0
- family_history: 0

Step 1:

Action taken: Improve sleep

Reward: 0.50

Info: {'action': 'Improve sleep', 'sleep_duration': '0.0 → 1.0'}

Current status of the student:

- age: 18.0
- gender: 1
- education: 3
- academic_pressure: 3.0
- study_satisfaction: 3.0
- study_hours: 7.143933296203613
- financial_stress: 3.0
- eating_habits: 0.0
- sleep_duration: 1.0
- depression: 1
- suicidal_thoughts: 0
- family_history: 0

Step 2:

Action taken: Improve diet

Reward: 0.50

Info: {'action': 'Improve diet', 'eating_habits': '0.0 → 1.0'}

Current status of the student:

- age: 18.0
- gender: 1
- education: 3
- academic_pressure: 3.0
- study_satisfaction: 3.0
- study_hours: 7.143933296203613
- financial_stress: 3.0
- eating_habits: 1.0
- sleep_duration: 1.0
- depression: 1
- suicidal_thoughts: 0
- family_history: 0

Step 3:

Action taken: Improve sleep

Reward: 0.50

Info: {'action': 'Improve sleep', 'sleep_duration': '1.0 → 2.0'}

Current status of the student:

- age: 18.0
- gender: 1
- education: 3
- academic_pressure: 3.0
- study_satisfaction: 3.0
- study_hours: 7.143933296203613
- financial_stress: 3.0
- eating_habits: 1.0
- sleep_duration: 2.0
- depression: 1
- suicidal_thoughts: 0
- family_history: 0

Step 4:

Action taken: Provide scholarship/financial aid

Reward: 0.40

Info: {'action': 'Provide scholarship/financial aid', 'change_financial_stress': '3.0 → 2.0'}

Current status of the student:

- age: 18.0
- gender: 1
- education: 3
- academic_pressure: 3.0
- study_satisfaction: 3.0
- study_hours: 7.143933296203613
- financial_stress: 2.0
- eating_habits: 1.0
- sleep_duration: 2.0
- depression: 1
- suicidal_thoughts: 0
- family_history: 0

Step 5:
Action taken: 0
Reward: 10.55
Info: {'accion': 'Decrease academic pressure', 'academic_pressure': '3.0 → 2.0', 'change_study_satisfaction': '3.0 → 4.0', 'change_study_hours': '7.1 → 5.6', 'depression_superada': True, 'final_reason': 'Depression overcome'}

Current status of the student:

- age: 18.0
- gender: 1
- education: 3
- academic_pressure: 2.0
- study_satisfaction: 4.0
- study_hours: 5.643933296203613
- financial_stress: 2.0
- eating_habits: 1.0
- sleep_duration: 2.0
- depression: 0
- suicidal_thoughts: 0
- family_history: 0

Total episode reward: 13.45